

METHODS OF TEACHING CHILDREN TO PLAY INSTRUMENTS IN HIGH SCHOOLS

Yaylovboeva Saida Azizbek kizi

Master of Namangan state university

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about various methods of organizing musical culture lessons, methods of teaching musical instruments to children by a music teacher.

Keywords: music, musical instruments, lesson, pedagogical technology, literature, method, creator, rubab, dutor, group.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada musiqa madaniyati darslarini tashkil etishning turli xil metodlari, musiqa o'qituvchisi tomonidan bolalarga cholg'u asboblarini o'rgatish usullari haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan

Kalit so'zlar: musiqa, musiqa asboblari, dars, pedagogik texnologiya, adabiyot, metod, ijodkor, rubob, dutor, guruh.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о различных методах организации уроков музыкальной культуры, методах обучения детей игре на музыкальных инструментах учителем музыки.

Ключевые слова: музыка, музыкальные инструменты, урок, педагогическая технология, литература, метод, творец, учитель, педагог, группа.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", of May 30, 2019 " On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay", "Shakhrisabz", "Termez" and "Kokand" Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 "On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts" Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 "Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3].Ensuring the development and prospects of the Republic of Uzbekistan depends on the changes taking place in the economic, social, political and cultural spheres, and in order to actively participate in such changes, high-level general and special knowledge, intellectual capacity, broad outlook and skillful use of information communications are required. Based on these requirements, the training of pedagogic personnel is one of the most important tasks of today.

Decree No. PD-6000 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev of May 26, 2020 “On measures to further increase the role and influence of the sphere of culture and art in the life of society”[4], Republic of Uzbekistan According to President Shavkat Mirziyoev’s Resolution No. PD-112 of February 2, 2022 “On additional measures for the further development of the sphere of culture and art”, starting from the 2022/2023 academic year, general education.

A music teacher should plan his lessons in such a way that he includes samples (at least a color picture) of Uzbek folk musical instruments in each lesson. In the first lesson, a musical instrument is introduced and a tune is played, and in the second lesson, a live performance and a piece performed on this instrument from a magnetic tape or diskette are played. In the third lesson, the teacher plays one of the Uzbek folk tunes, and the children accompany with clappers, safoil, spoons, and sticks. This is definitely achieved by teaching children to accompany during the lessons. In primary grades, students are introduced to Uzbek musical instruments by groups of musical instruments. For example, first with wind instruments, then with stringed percussion instruments, then with percussion instruments, and so on. Bringing samples of Uzbek musical instruments to the lesson by the music teacher is the most interesting part of the lesson for children. Because adult musical instruments are interesting to every child as live and real musical instruments. Musical instruments are primarily important for the development of creativity and musical learning skills in children through performance elements. When a musical instrument is played by the teacher, it helps the children to express themselves and be active in the lesson.

The musical instrument brought to the lesson is an instructional didactic guide in teaching, which can help the teacher to develop the musical-sensory abilities of the child, as well as introduce the elements of music literacy. As a result of observations, the teacher can form a small ensemble or orchestra 151 from the children, taking into account the talents and capabilities of the class children. Participating in an ensemble or orchestra requires a certain degree of equipment availability and training in: Names of children’s musical instruments, playing character, pitch and pitch (low and high) placement, use and with the rules of dealing, they learn playing methods, they can perform songs and games independently and in an ensemble, observing the general dynamics and tempo, starting and ending their tracks in time. New ones are added to well-tested methods of work - demonstration and oral explanation. It is recommended that

the child play the given instrument without the help of the teacher, remember the sequence of playing one or another instrument, perform creative tasks, and so on. Musical instruments should be mastered in turn. First, a child can be introduced to playing an instrument, for example, a circle, and during several lessons, it can be taught to accompany two or three small pieces. Sometimes it is also useful to examine the instrument together with the children, correct them when they make mistakes, and entrust them to find a way to play it independently.[5]

At the same time, it is possible to master the instruments that provide rhythm. At the first stage, it is necessary to teach the child to the harmonious actions of cooperation necessary for his participation in the ensemble. For this purpose, special “rhythmic orchestras” are formed, in which children clap their hands, tap their feet, knock on sticks, empty or small stones, and boxes filled with peas. Here too, voting is formed differently.

If you clap with your palms together, the sound will be harder and muffled, if your palms are in a flat position, the sound will be clear and sonorous. The sound can be changed by striking the palm of the other hand with the extended or slightly bent fingers of one hand. Tapping is done with the whole leg, with the tip of the foot, with the heel, alternately with the tip of the foot and the heel. All this will attract the child, allow him to correctly perform various rhythmic tasks and acquire the skills of playing a musical instrument.

Experiments show that the presence of percussion instruments such as circle, drum, safoil, claret, and spoon in the lesson gives good results. The teacher plays the children's bop from 152 Uzbek folk tunes on the rubab (dutor, any other instrument) and invites the children to join in with clapping.

From the beginning, if the teacher claps beautifully and correctly, the teacher tells him that he will accompany the music by playing the percussion instruments on the table as a “reward”. If there is a melody to be played on a magnetic tape or a diskette, it will be better if he first shows the clapping method by playing it. Then he performs the tune himself, invites everyone to join in clapping to the tune, and carefully monitors the performance process, distributing percussion instruments to the children. The achievements and shortcomings of the first implementation are explained.

After this performance is first accompanied by playing instruments, the rest of the children are invited to accompany with clappers. Everyone aspires to play musical instruments, of course. That's why the musicians change. In time, when children develop good skills in these performances, the structure of the method

and the types of performance become a little more complicated. For example, you can accompany the “Andijan Polka” by playing instruments and clapping your hands, saying “Bum-bak, bakkabum” in your mouth.[6] In this case, the class can be divided into two groups, and the first group will play clapping and instruments, and the second group will accompany the singing, and even invite a child who wants to dance on the stage of the class. In another option, the teacher plays the “Bum bak-ka” method clearly and evenly in the circle. Children of the first group follow the “Bum” method, and children of the second group follow the “Wak-ka” method.

After familiarizing yourself with the graphic image of the melody displayed on the board and the images of quarter and half notes equal to its rhythmic structure, it is easy to perform such an exercise based on the rhythmic structure of the melody created with the help of cards on the board.

Such classes, first of all, make the content of the lesson interesting, because it helps them to get acquainted with the world of Uzbek folk musical instruments, activates the students' activities, ensures the comprehensive development of their creativity, performance skills, and music-learning abilities. In general, a great creativity and ingenuity is required from the teacher when learning and playing Uzbek folk instruments in the lesson.

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